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Research Article

PROGRESS OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN PAKISTAN**Dr Ayesha Faiz¹, Dr Fasiha Hanif², Dr Muhammad Abdullah Usman³, Dr Fiza Anwer⁴**¹Services Institute of Medical Sciences, SHL²Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore³Xinjiang Medical University Urumqi China**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

The outbreak of coronavirus initiated as pneumonia of unknown cause in December 2019 in Wuhan, China, which has been now spreading rapidly out of Wuhan to other countries. The main objective of the study is to analyse the progress of COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan. This descriptive study was conducted in Services Institute of Medical sciences, during January 2020 to June 2020. We collect the data from different sources and then analyse the progress of COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan. According to Pakistan's last update on April 10, 54 706 suspected coronavirus cases were reported in Pakistan, 4695 of which tested positive for COVID-19 (8.6%). Of the 4695 cases, 727 patients recovered (15.5%), 45 remain critical (1%), and 66 died (CFR: 1.4%). Coronavirus attack rate is estimated to be 2.3 per 100 000 Pakistani population. Nearly 49% of cases are registered from Punjab. It is concluded that the rate of transmission of COVID-19 in Pakistan appears to be small if we compare with other countries. It has been postulated that the low rate of infection may be attributed to many reasons such as humid conditions, hot weather, tropical conditions, widespread BCG vaccinations and relatively government's precautionary measures.

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INTRODUCTION:

The outbreak of coronavirus initiated as pneumonia of unknown cause in December 2019 in Wuhan, China, which has been now spreading rapidly out of Wuhan to other countries. On January 30, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared COVID-19 outbreak as the sixth public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC), and on March 11, 2020, the WHO announced COVID-19 as pandemic. On April 9, 2020, nearly 1 436 198 cases of 2019-novel coronavirus recorded out of which 85 522 died with a case fatality rate (CFR) of 5.95%. The WHO evaluated the global risk of COVID-19 as very high. In the coming days and weeks, the amount of events, fatalities, and affected countries is projected to increase sharply [1].

Corona virus belongs to a coronaviridae family. At the end of 2019, Wuhan an emerging business hub of China experienced an outbreak of corona virus which killed more than 1,800 people and infected more than 70,000 people during first five days of the epidemic [2]. This corona virus is named as the novel corona virus disease 2019 (2019-nCoV) by Chinese researchers. The international committee on Taxonomy of viruses (ICTV) named the virus as SARS-COV-2 and the disease as COVID-19.1 Corona virus is small in size 65-125 nm in diameter and contains a single stranded Ribonucleic acid (RNA) as nucleic material size ranging from 26 to 32 kbs in length [3].

COVID-19 works like a typical respiratory coronavirus in the basic mechanism, infections and replications. But some mutations allow it to bind tighter to host receptor and increase its transmissibility, which is thought to make it more infective. Researchers have found that severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) was detectable in aerosols for up to three hours, up to four hours on copper, up to 24 hours on cardboard and up to two to three days on plastic and stainless steel [3]. The results provide key information about the stability of SARS-CoV-2, which causes COVID-19 disease, and suggests that people may obtain the virus through the air and after touching contaminated objects. More than hundred years since the outbreak of the 1918 influenza pandemic, we now have another pandemic in our hands. The

outbreak of COVID-19 infection is spreading to everywhere in the world, forcing us to live with this virus for perhaps a long time [4]. Scientists and professionals have continued to be educated on COVID-19 and its complicated pathogenesis and presentation. For example, not all people exposed to COVID-19 are symptomatic and not all infected patients develop severe respiratory infection. Consequently, COVID-19 infection can be roughly classified into three phases: phase I, an asymptomatic incubation period with or without noticeable virus; phase II, non-severe symptomatic period with the occurrence of virus; and phase III, severe respiratory symptomatic phase with high viral load [5].

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to analyse the progress of COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive study was conducted in Services Institute of Medical sciences, during January 2020 to June 2020. We collect the data from different sources and then analyse the progress of COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan. According to Pakistan's last update on April 10, 54 706 suspected coronavirus cases were reported in Pakistan, 4695 of which tested positive for COVID-19 (8.6%). Of the 4695 cases, 727 patients recovered (15.5%), 45 remain critical (1%), and 66 died (CFR: 1.4%). Coronavirus attack rate is estimated to be 2.3 per 100 000 Pakistani population. Nearly 49% of cases are registered from Punjab. The cumulative reported cases of COVID in Punjab increased by 53.2% (1493 cases to 2287 cases) from April 5 to 10. Sindh recorded the second highest number of incidences (26%) followed by Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK; 13.2%). From April 5 to 10, the cumulative reported cases of COVID increased by 28% (881 cases to 1128 cases) in Sindh and in KPK from 205 cases to 620 cases. Azad Jammu Kashmir (AJK) recorded the lowest number of incidences (0.7%) followed by Islamabad (2.3%). District wise, 880 cases have been confirmed from Lahore (19%) and 871 cases from Karachi (18.9%). Gilgit Baltistan (GB) has the highest rate of recovery (52%), while KPK has the lowest rate of mortality (3.5%) compared with other regions of Pakistan [6].

Pakistan situation report (April 10, 2020)

DISCUSSION:

Recently, the incidence of COVID-19 has increased due to travel to other parts of the world. Pakistan has trade and travel with Iran and China. The increased influx of travelers through land, air, and sea put Pakistan at higher odds of further spread of coronavirus from neighboring countries. The possibility of further importation of the virus into Pakistan is very high, and because Pakistan has already imported the virus, the country needs to take stringent measures to detect potential cases early in order to curb existing epidemic and tracking steps to prevent further spread. After the unexpected rise in coronavirus cases in Pakistan, the Government of Pakistan has halted trade and transport operations with Iran [7]. Now owing to severe snowfall the land connection with China is blocked. Whereas mobilization is tightly controlled at the boundaries of Chaman and Taftan. Additionally, it monitors external travel to Iraq, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and Iran. Weekly, 41 flights operate in Pakistan from 3 cities (Karachi, Islamabad, and Lahore) and to 2 destinations in China (Urumqi and Beijing). The danger of virus importation into Pakistan is very high and needs good precautions and strict steps to identify possible cases early and surveillance steps to deter further virus transmission. Pakistan is still in the containment process. The step to shutdown point of entry and borders has been taken. All international flights have been cancelled. In this way, the number of cases might not increase as most of the spread was through worldwide migrants and yet it is impossible to find the point of origin [8].

With increasing cases of immensely contagious COVID-19, Pakistan's economy is under great deterioration. The terror of fatal disease and economic distress have come up together. The country cannot bear extended lockdown and should the lockdown extend, Pakistan will suffer unmanageable economic loss. Pakistan does not have any sufficient resources to provide for the patients at the moment [1]. Most of the populace is working on daily wages. The shutdown of the whole

country would cause death either due to hunger or from COVID-19. The current statement of Pakistan's prime minister calls for a community meeting among susceptible countries that are dealing with the pandemic. It has been decided that rather than complete shutdown, people should avoid mass gatherings, and partial shutting down of the country will take place in order for the economy to provide for basic necessities [3].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that the rate of transmission of COVID-19 in Pakistan appears to be small if we compare with other countries. It has been postulated that the low rate of infection may be attributed to many reasons such as humid conditions, hot weather, tropical conditions, widespread BCG vaccinations and relatively government's precautionary measures. The lives and livelihood of Pakistan citizens as well as that of the world is at stake due to pandemic. There are still many uncertainties about how the pandemic would be controlled in Pakistan if the virus re-emerges.

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